

What are users doing with my features?

This questionnaire aims at gathering your opinion about the ideas express in this seminar.

We thank you a lot for you cooperation.

Concretely the questionnaire asks about:

- (1) expected benefits of implicit feedback in SPLE,
- (2) appropriateness of introducing implicit feedback into SPLE processes as described in the seminar
- (3) perceived usefulness and ease of use of the **FEACKER** tool for *pure::variants* to support implicit feedback

* Indicates required question

Informed consent

Please read this consent agreement carefully before you decide to participate.

In this study, you will complete a survey of the diagnosing students' misunderstandings. In total it will take you about 10 minutes to answer it divided in three parts. Filling out this questionnaire does not imply any risk or personal benefit.

Confidentiality.

Your data will be recorded, stored, and shared **anonymously**.

Right to withdraw

Your participation in the study is completely voluntary. You have the right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty by closing the survey window.

Contact.

If you have questions about the study, contact:

- Raul Medeiros, raul.medeiros@ehu.eus

- Oscar Diaz, oscar.diaz@ehu.eus

University of the Basque Country, Facultad de Informática, San Sebastian (Spain)

Demographics

This section gathers anonymous data about your professional experience

1. How many years of experience on SPL do you have? *
-

2. How many years of experience at *pure::system* do you have? *

3. How would you characterize your main working role? *

Mark only one oval.

Developer

Tester

Project Manager

Consultant

Other: _____

FIRST PART: Introducing implicit feedback into SPLE processes

We want to assess your opinion about appropriateness of introducing implicit feedback into SPLE processes as described in the seminar. We refer to this process as IF4SPL (Implicit Feedback for SPL). The process is divided in four different activities:

-Feedback specification: the specification of the feature feedback needs at the level of the SPL platform

-Feedback transformation: the incorporation of feature tracking into variants at transformation time

-Feedback gathering: the collection of the implicit feedback into the feedback log.

-Feedback analysis: the study of the Feedback log for decision making

COHERENCE: the quality of forming a unified whole with traditional SPLE practices

This section gathers your opinion on how well does IF4SPL integrate with current SPLE practices

4. In general, I consider IF4SPL a natural fit to current SPLE practices *

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

5. I consider **the `Feedback Specification` task** (see def. above) a natural fit to current SPLE practices *

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

6. I consider **Feedback Transformation** (see def. above) a natural fit to current SPLE practices *

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

7. I consider **Feedback Gathering** (see def. above) fits well with current SPLE practices *

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

8. I consider '**Feedback analysis**' (see def. above) a natural fit to current SPLE practices *

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

CONSISTENCY: the quality of seamlessly fit with prior roles in SPLE (Application Engineer & Domain Engineer)

9. In general, I would consider that IF4SPLE does not alter the traditional role distribution among the SPL task force

*

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

10. I would favor **Feedback Specification** (see def. above) to be performed by **Domain Engineers** at the **Platform** level *

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

11. I would favor **Feedback Specification** (see def. above) to be performed by **Application Engineers** at the **Variant** level *

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

12. I would favor **Feedback Analysis** (see def. above) to be performed by **Domain * Engineers** at the **Platform** level

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

13. I would favor **Feedback Analysis** (see def. above) to be performed by **Application Engineers** at the **Variant** level *

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

14. Add any other comment about IF4SPLE

END OF THE FIRST PART

SECOND PART: The FEACKER component

This section assess the extent FEACKER seamlessly integrate with *pure::variants* in terms of perceived usefulness and ease of use

PERCEIVED USEFULNESS

15. Using FEACKER would enable me to accomplish IF4SPL tasks more quickly *

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

16. Using FEACKER would improve my performance following IF4SPL *

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

17. Using FEACKER for folowing IF4SPLE would increase my productivity *

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

18. Using FEACKER would enhance my effectiveness on following IF4SPLE *

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

19. Using FEACKER would make it easier to follow IF4SPLE *

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

20. I would find FEACKER useful in following IF4SPLE *

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

PERCEIVED EASE OF USE

21. Learning to operate FEACKER would be easy for me *

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

22. I would find it easy to get FEACKER to do what I want it to do *

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

23. My interaction with FEACKER would be clear and understandable *

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

24. I would find FEACKER to be flexible to interact with *

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

25. I would find FEACKER easy to use *

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

26. It would be easy for me to become skillful at using FEACKER *

Mark only one oval.

Completely Disagree

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Completely Agree

27. Add any other comment about FEACKER

Thank you very much for filling out the questionnaire!

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